

POLAND

POLAND

**FORMAL TILLAR VA GRAMMATIKA.KOMPYUTER
LINGVISTIKASINI KASHF ETILISHIDAGI MATEMATIK MODELLAR
KO'RINISHI.**

Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, 1-bosqich magistrant.
maqsudu32@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560898>

Anotatsiya: Bu maqola axborot texnologiyalari rivojlanayotgan bir paytda yuzaga kelayotgan kompyuter lingvistikasining o'ziga xos yo'nalishlari va modellari haqida tushuncha beradi. Zamon talabiga mos holda matematik modellarni hamko'rib chiqish mumkin bo'ladi.

Kompyuter lingvistikasi asosida matematik lingvistikani kelib chiqishini kuzatish mumkin va maqolda bu haqida to'xtalib o'tiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: kompyuter lingvistikasi, virtual standlar, yondashuv, mashina tarjimasi, matematik model, tabiiy til unsurlari.

Annotation: This article provides an insight into the specific trends and models of computer linguistics that are emerging at a time when information technology is evolving. Mathematical models can also be considered in accordance with modern requirements. The origins of mathematical linguistics can be traced back to computerlinguistics, and the article discusses this.

Keywords: computer linguistics, virtual stands, approach, machine translation, mathematical model, natural language elements

Hozirgi kunda Axborot - kommunikasion texnologiyalarining rivojlanish bosqichida ijtimoiy sohaning o'qitish jarayoniga ham zamonaviy texnologiyalarning tadbiiq etilishi zamon talablaridan biriga aylanmoqda. Shu jumladan an'anaviy ta'limni kompyuterli o'qitish tizimlari orqali takomillashtirish hamda boyitish tabiiy ravishda mutaxassislar oldiga yangicha yondashuvlar va uslubiy vositalarini ishlab chiqish kabi bir qator masalalarni qo'ymoqda. Axborot texnologiyalarini ta'lim jarayoniga joriy etish bo'yicha jamiyatimizning tez sur'atlar bilan o'sib boruvchi ehtiyojlari oliy ta'lim muassasalarida auditoriya va auditoriyadan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda elektron qo'llanmalar, virtual standlar, Internet tarmog'I imkoniyatlaridan foydalangan holda masofaviy o'qitish, shuningdek, masofaviy ta'limni joriy etish bilan bog'liq izchil nazariy hamda amaliy tadbirlar bajarilishini taqozo etadi. O'zbekistonda masofaviy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanishi, xalqimizga faqat sifatli ta'lim berishnigina ta'minlab qolmasdan, u yana mamlakatimizning ta'lim xizmatlari xalqaro bozorida o'z o'rnini egallashiga ham imkon yaratadi. Kompyuterli o'qitishni tashkil etish va rivojlantirish bo'yicha bir qator

yo'nalishda ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi birinchi Prezidentining 2002- yil 30-mayda qabul qilingan—Kompyuterlashtirishni yanada rivojlantirish va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risidagi qarorda kadrlar tayyorlash sohasini takomillashtirish, mamlakatimiz salohiyatini oshirishning demokratik davlat va bozor iqtisodiyotiga asoslangan fuqarolik jamiyati qurishning muhim shartlaridan biri sifatida belgilandi.

Hozirgi kunda kompyuter vositalarning texnik va dasturiy ta'minoti darajasi ancha yuqori bo'lib, bu barcha sohada olib borilayotgan ishlarni qanoatlantirmoqda. O'qitishning kompyuterli tizimlarida ham bilimlar bazasini shakllantirish avtomatlashtirilgan o'qitish tizimlari tamoyillari bilan ishlovchi tizimlarni yanada yuqori bosqichga, ya'ni intellektual o'qitish tizimlari bosqichiga ko'tarishga xizmat qiladi. Kompyuter tizimini tilshunoslik fani bilan bo'lash juda muhim hisoblanadi. Ma'lumki, tilshunoslik fani XIX asrda mustaqil fan sifatida shakllandi. Shundan boshlab u turli aspektlarda, yo'nalishlarda rivojlanib kelmoqda. Jumladan, ana shunday fanlar sirasiga sotsiologiya (sotsiologiya va tilshunoslik), psixolingvistik (psixologiya va tilshunoslik), etnolingvistik (etnografiya va lingvistik), neyrolingvistik (nevrologiya va tilshunoslik), matematik lingvistik va kompyuter lingvistikasi fanlarini kiritish mumkin. Buni fanlar tizimida bir necha fanlarning o'zaro hamkorligi, integratsiyasi deb baholash lozim bo'ladi. XX asrning o'rtalaridan boshlab tilshunoslikda «mashina tarjimai», «mashina tilshunosligi» atamaları qo'llanila boshlandi. Shu tariqa mashina tarjimai g'oyalari butun dunyoda nazariy va amaliy tilshunoslikning rivojlanishida katta ahamiyat kasb etdi. Bu yo'nalish bilan parallel ravishda formal grammatika nazariyasi yuzaga kelib, til va uning alohida aspektlari modelini yaratishga e'tibor qaratildi. Tilning bu jihatlari matematik lingvistik fanida ishlab chiqildi, bu, o'z navbatida, kompyuter lingvistikasi fanining yuzaga kelishi uchun poydevor bo'ldi. Demak, shu asosda tilshunoslikning yangi yo'nalishi - kompyuter lingvistikasi va tilshunoslikning bir qator nazariy va amaliy yo'nalishlari vujudga keldi. Matematik lingvistik fani XX asrning 50-yillarida tilshunoslikning alohida yo'nalishi sifatida yuzaga keldi. Bu fanning shakllanishida Kopengagen struktural tilshunoslik maktabi (glossematika)ning asoschisi Lui Yelmslevning g'oyalari o'ziga xos «turtki» vazifasini o'tagan. U hatto til hodisalarini matematik bayonda tushuntiradigan fanning nomini ham taklif etgan. Olimning fikricha, bu fan «Til algebrasi» («Lingvistik algebra») deb atalishi lozim edi. Amerikalik tilshunos Noam Chomskiyning formal grammatika, transformatsion grammatika haqidagi

qarashlari bevosita matematik lingvistikaning alohida yo'nalish sifatida yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'lgan. Mana shunday qarashlar ta'sirida matematik lingvistika fani shakllandi. Matematik lingvistika - bu tabiiy tillarning matematik ishlab chiqish, xususan, sun'iy tillarni yaratish algoritmini tuzish bilan shug'ullanuvchi fandır. Matematik lingvistika oldida turuvchi eng muhim masalalar quyidagilardir:

- tilning aksiomatik nazariyasini ishlab chiqish;
- formal grammatika yaratish;
- tillarning matematik modellarini ishlab chiqish.

Matematik lingvistika fanining asosiy maqsadi tabiiy tillarning matematik modelini ishlab chiqishdir. Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun fan o'z oldiga quyidagi vazifalarni qo'yadi:

- tabiiy va sun'iy tillarning formal modellari ishlab chiqish;
- lisoniy hodisalarni matematik parametrlarda baholash;
- til hodisalarini matematik metodlar yordamida tahlil qilish.

Kompyuter lingvistikasi matematik lingvistikaning mantiqiy davomi bo'lib, u amaliy tilshunoslikning eng muhim qismini tashkil etadi va kompyuter lingvistikasi AQShda 1954- yilda Jorjtaun universitetida mashina tarjimai bo'yicha dunyoda o'tkazilgan birinchi tajriba asnosida yo'nalish sifatida shakllana boshlandi ham 1960- yilga kelib mustaqil fan sifatida faoliyat olib bordi. Kompyuter lingvistikasi inglizcha

«computational linguistics» so'zining asosidir. XX asrning 80-yillariga qadar bu fan turlicha nomlar bilan atalgan ya'ni hisoblash lingvistikasi, matematik lingvistika, kvantitativ lingvistika kabi nomlar bilan yuritilgan.

Bu fanning asosiy maqsadi lingvistik masalalarni yechishning kompyuter dasturlarini ishlab chiqish, inson va mashina (kompyuter) muloqotini optimallashtirish, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlashdir. Tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash kompyuter lingvistikasida tabiiy tillarning kompyuter analizi va sintezini o'z ichiga oladi. Bunda analiz tabiiy tilning kompyuterda morfologik, sintaktik va semantik tahlil yordamida tushunilishiga nisbatan ishlatiladi, sintez esa kompyuterda matnning grammatik shakllantirilishi va generatsiyasini anglatadi.

Kompyuter lingvistikasining asosiy yo'nalishlariga quyidagilar kiradi:

- avtomatik o'qitish tizimini ishlab chiqish;
- bilimlarni tekshirish;
- matnlarni turli jihatdan avtomatik tahrirlash;
- matnlarning avtomatik tarzda morfologik, sintaktik va semantik

tahlilnita'minlovchi tizimlar yaratish;

- mashina tarjimasini uchun mo'ljallangan dasturlarni ishlab chiqish;
- lug'atlarni va kompyuterdagi matnni statistik tahlil qilish;
- lingvistik muammolarni hal qilishga yo'naltirilgan optimal dasturlar yaratish;
- muloqotning kompyuter modelini ishlab chiqish;
- matn strukturasi gipertekst texnologiyasini yaratish va boshqalardir.

Kompyuter lingvistikasi esa amaliy xarakterga ega bo'lib, til bilan bog'liq muammolarning amaliy jihatiga e'tibor qaratadi. Kompyuter lingvistikasida esa ko'proq sun'iy tillar (programmallashtirish tillari, algoritmik tillar)ga tayaniladi, tabiiy tillarning mavjud imkoniyatlari cheklanadi, bunda tabiiy tilga ishlov berilib, kompyuterga moslashtiriladi. Buning uchun model atamasini ham esdan chiqarmaslik zarur. Model bizga sistemaning o'rganish, tushunish, izohlash, mukammallashtirish sohasida yordam berishi mumkin bo'lgan vosita hisoblanadi. Model biror ob'ektni to'la va aniq yoki biror bir xususiyatlarini ifodalashi mumkin. Ob'ektning absolyut aniq modeli uning o'zidir. + olgan barcha modellar taqribiy model hisoblanadi. Model – bu mantiqiy yo'l bilan u yoki bu xarakter natijasini bashorat qilish yoki qiyoslashga imkon beruvchi vosita bo'lib, oqibatda qilinishi mumkin bo'lgan xarakterlardan eng yaxshisini tanlab ko'rsata oladi va eng ko'p qo'llaniluvchi model bu matematik modellardir. Odatda, matematik model ustida hisoblash tajribasini o'tkazish haqiqiy obyektning tajribada taqiq etish mumkin bo'lmagan yoki iqtisodiy jihatdan maqsadga muvofiq bo'lmagan hollarda o'tkaziladi. Bunday hisoblash tajribasining natijalari haqiqiy ob'yekt ustida olib boriladigan tajribaga qaraganda juda aniq emasligini ham hisobga olish kerak. Lekin shunday misollarni keltirish mumkinki, kompyuterda o'tkazilgan hisoblash tajribasi o'rganilayotgan jarayon yoki hodisa haqidagi ishonchli axborotning yagona manbai bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Masalan, faqat matematik modellashtirish va kompyuterda hisoblash tajribasini o'tkazish yo'li bilan yadroviy urushning iqlimga ta'siri oqibatlarini oldindan aytib berish mumkin. Kompyuter yadro qurolli urushda mutlaq g'olib bo'lmasligini ko'rsatadi.

Kompyuterli tajriba Yer yuzida bunday urush oqibatida ekologik o'zgarishlar, ya'ni haroratning keskin o'zgarishi, atmosferaning changlanishi, qutblardagi muzliklarning erishining ro'y berishi, xatto, Yer o'z o'qidan chiqib ketishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Matematik modellashtirishda berilgan fizik jarayonlarning matematik ifodalari modelashtiriladi. Matematik model tashqi dunyoning

matematik belgilar bilan ifodalangan qandaydir hodisalar sinfiningtaqribiy tavsifidir. Matematik model tashqi dunyoni bilish, shuningdek, oldindan aytib berish va boshqarishning kuchli uslubi hisoblanadi. Matematik modelni tahlil qilish o'rganilayotgan hodisaning mohiyatiga singish imkoniyatini beradi. Hodisalarni matematik model yordamida o'rganish to'rt bosqichda amalga oshiriladi.

Birinchi bosqich - modelning asosiy ob'yektlarini bog'lovchi qonunlarni ifodalash.

Ikkinchi bosqich - modeldagi matematik masalalarni tekshirish.

Uchinchi bosqich - modelning qabul qilingan amaliyot mezonlarini qanoatlantirishni aniqlash.

Boshqacha aytganda, modeldan olingan nazariy natijalar bilan olingan ob'yektni kuzatish natijalari mos kelishi masalasini aniqlash.

To'rtinchi bosqich - o'rganilayotgan hodisa haqidagi ma'lumotlarni jamlash orqali modelning navbatdagi tahlilini o'tkazish va uni rivojlantirish, aniqlashtirish.

Shunday qilib, modellashtirishning asosiy mazmunini ob'yektni dastlabki o'rganish asosida modelni tajriba orqali va nazariy tahlil qilish, natijalarni ob'yekt haqidagi ma'lumotlar bilan taqqoslash, modelni tuzatish (takomillashtirish) va shu kabilar tashkil etadi.

Matematik model tuzish uchun, dastlab masala rasmiylashtiriladi. Masala mazmuniga mos holda zarur belgilar kiritiladi. So'ngra kattaliklar orasida formula yoki algoritm ko'rinishida yozilgan funksional bog'lanish hosil qilinadi. Aytib o'tilganlarni aniq misolda ko'rib chiqamiz.

Talaba o'ylagan son matematik fokusga mos model yordamida aniqlanadi. Masalani rasmiylashtiramiz: X - o'quvchi o'ylagan son, U - hisoblash natijasi, N - sana, M - joriy yil.

Demak, olib boruvchining ko'rsatmalari:

$$U = (X \cdot 5 + N) \cdot 2 + M$$

formula orqali ifodalanadi.

Ushbu formula masalaning (matematik fokusning) matematik modeli bo'lib xizmat qiladi va X o'zgaruvchiga nisbatan chiziqli tenglamani ifodalaydi.

Tenglamani yechamiz:

$$X = (U - (M + 2N)) / 10$$

Ushbu formula o'ylagan sonni topish algoritmini ko'rsatadi.

XXI asr axborot texnologiyalari asrida o'quvchilar kompyuter, internetdan bemalol foydalanadi va bunga bo'lgan qiziqishlari yuqori ekani hech kimga sir

emas. Shunday ekan o`quvchilarga darslarni axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari orqali o`tsak o`quvchilarning qiziqishlari ortadi. Masalan maktab matematika kursidagi arifmetik progressiya yoki geometrik progressiyaning hadlarini chiqaruvchi dasturni Pascal dasturlash muhitida ko`rib o`tsak.

Arifmetik progressiyani bu usulda hadlarini ko`rsatish jarayonida o`quvchining kompyuter savodxonligi oshadi, shuning barobarida matematik bilimi mustahkamlanadi. Umuman olganda matematika darslarini axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari orqali slaydlarda animatsiya va gipersilka yordamida dars ishlanamaları tayyorlanib o`tilsa, o`quvchilarni qiziqishlari yuqori darajada bo`ladi.

```

Program progressiya;
Uses crt;
var a1,d: real;
i,n: integer;
begin
write('Birinchi hadini kiriting a[1]='); read(a1);
write('Ayirmasini kiriting d='); read(d);
write('Hadlarini sonini kiriting n='); read(n);
writeln('1-hadi a[1]=',a1,' ga teng');
for i:=2 to n do begin
a1:=a1+d;
writeln(i,'-hadi a[',i,']=',a1,' ga teng');
end;
write('Dasturchi: F.Xasanov');
end.

```

```

CRT - программа завершена
Birinchi hadini kiriting a[1]=2
Ayirmasini kiriting d=3
Hadlarini sonini kiriting n=15
1-hadi a[1]=2 ga teng
2-hadi a[2]=5 ga teng
3-hadi a[3]=8 ga teng
4-hadi a[4]=11 ga teng
5-hadi a[5]=14 ga teng
6-hadi a[6]=17 ga teng
7-hadi a[7]=20 ga teng
8-hadi a[8]=23 ga teng
9-hadi a[9]=26 ga teng
10-hadi a[10]=29 ga teng
11-hadi a[11]=32 ga teng
12-hadi a[12]=35 ga teng
13-hadi a[13]=38 ga teng
14-hadi a[14]=41 ga teng
15-hadi a[15]=44 ga teng
Dasturchi: F.Xasanov_

```

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro`yxati:

1. Usmonov, M. T. o`g`li. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini tuzatish usullari. Fan va ta`lim, 2(8), 280-291. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1758> dan olindi.
2. Usmonov, M. T. o`g`li. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. Fan va ta`lim, 2(8), 226-238. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1752> dan olindi.
3. Usmonov, M. T. o`g`li. (2021). Vektorlar. Fan va ta`lim, 2(8), 173-182. <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1747> dan olindi.
4. Usmonov, M. T. o`g`li. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar tizimini echishning matritsa, Gauss va Gauss-Jordan usullari. Fan va ta`lim, 2(8), 312-322. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1761> dan olindi.
5. Usmonov, M. T. o`g`li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta`lim, 2(8), 133-145. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

6. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 146-152. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
7. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 153-172. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1746> dan olindi.
8. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 109-120. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1742> dan olindi.
9. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 183-191. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1748> dan olindi.
10. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko'paytmalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 271-279. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1757> dan olindi.
11. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor formulasini matematik masalalarni echishdagi ahamiyati. "«Science and Education» Scientific Journal" Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 19-23.
12. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Darajali qatorlarning taqribiy hisoblashlarga tatbiqi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 29-32.
13. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Ishoralari almashinib keluvchi qatorlar. Leybnits alomati. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 24-28.
14. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor qatori va uning tadbiqlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 33-38.
15. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление центра тяжести плоской ограниченной фигуры с помощью двойного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 64-71.
16. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Биномиальное распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 81-85.
17. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Поток векторного поля. Поток через замкнутую поверхность. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 52-63.
18. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Вычисление определенного интеграла по формуле трапеций и методом Симпсона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 213-225.
19. Усмонов,М.Т. (2021). Метод касательных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 25-34.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

20. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление предела функции с помощью ряда. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 92-96.
21. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Примеры решений произвольных тройных интегралов. Физические приложения тройного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 39-51.
22. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла в полярной системе координат. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-108.
23. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейный интеграл по замкнутому контуру. Формула Грина. Работа векторного поля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 72-80.
24. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Правило Крамера. Метод обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 249-255.
25. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Теоремы сложения и умножения вероятностей. Зависимые и независимые события. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 202-212.
26. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Распределение и формула Пуассона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-91.
27. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Геометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 18-24.
28. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади поверхности вращения. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-104.
29. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Нахождение обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 123-130.
30. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла. Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 192-201.
31. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод прямоугольников. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 105-112.
32. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Как вычислить длину дуги кривой?. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-96.
33. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади фигуры в полярных координатах с помощью интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 77-85.
34. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Повторные пределы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 35-43.
35. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Дифференциальные уравнения второго порядка и высших порядков. Линейные дифференциальные уравнения второго

POLAND

POLAND

порядка с постоянными коэффициентами. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 113-122.

36. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Пределы функций. Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 139-150.

37. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод наименьших квадратов. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 54-65.

38. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Непрерывность функции двух переменных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 44-53.

39. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Интегрирование корней (иррациональных функций). Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 239-248.

40. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейные интегралы. Понятие и примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 26-38.

41. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Гипергеометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 19-25.

42. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Абсолютная и условная сходимость несобственного интеграла. Признак Дирихле. Признак Абеля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 66-76.

43. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Решение систем линейных уравнений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 131-138.

44. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 226-238.

45. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 292-302.

46. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 323-331.

47. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 121-132.

48. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 183-191.

49. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 146-152.

50. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 303-311.

51. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 173-182.

52. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 153-172.
53. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 109-120.
54. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 133-145.
55. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 256-270.
56. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 280-291.
57. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Autentification, authorization and administration. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 233-242.
58. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
59. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). EHTIMOLLAR NAZARIYASI. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 10-15.
60. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 333-311.
61. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-21, 323-331.
62. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
63. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 121-132.
64. Usmonov M. T. & Qodirov F. E, BIR JINSLI VA BIR JINSLIGA OLIB KELINADIGAN DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. AMALIY MASALALARGA TADBIQI (KO'ZGU MASALASI) , BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: Vol. 2 No. 1 (2022): БАРҚАРОРЛИК ВА ЕТАКЧИ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ
65. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, BIRINCHI VA IKKINCHI TARTIBLI HUSUSIY HOSILALAR. TO'LA DIFFERENSIAL. TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH , BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022: SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI
66. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, IKKI ARGUMENTLI

FUNKSIYANING ANIQLANISH SOHASI, GRAFIGI, LIMITI VA UZLUKSIZLIGI ,
BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022:
SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH
ISTIQBOLLARI

67. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li. (2022). FURYE QATORI. FUNKSIYALARNI
FURYE QATORIGA YOYISH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6055125>

68. Usmonov. M. T. , & Qodirov. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR.
DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR
FORMULASI VA QATORI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY
JURNALI, 8–20. Retrieved from
<http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>

69. Usmonov. M. T. , & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING
TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21–
33. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>

70. M.T Usmonov, M.A Turdiyeva, Y.Q Shoniyozova, (2021). SAMPLE POWER.
SELECTION METHODS (SAMPLE ORGANIZATION METHODS). ООО НАУЧНАЯ
ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА , 59-60.

71. Усмонов,М.Т, М.А.Турдиева (2021). ГЛАВА 9. МЕТОДЫ И СРЕДСТВА
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ СЕТЕЙ. РИСКИ И ПРИНЦИПЫ
ЗАЩИТЫ ИНФОРМАЦИИ В ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ ПОЧТЕ. ББК 60 С69, Ст-99.

72. Усмонов,М.Т, J.M.Saipnazarov, К.В. Ablaqulov (2021 SOLUTION OF
MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS IN LOWER CLASSES. Книга: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ
ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, 167-177.

73. Усмонов М.Т. (2022). E-LEARNING И ЕГО РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ
СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. : Special Issue_Та'limni modernizatsiyalash
jarayonlari muammolar va echimlar». 168-171.

74. Usmonov. M. T. , & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). STOKS FORMULASI. SIRT
INTEGRALLARI TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN
ILMIY JURNALI, 34–45. Retrieved from
<https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1153>

75. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility.
International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR), Vol. 5
Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.

76. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept
of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Information
Systems Research (IJASR), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 7-9.

77. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 66-68.
78. Usmonov M. T. General Concept of Mathematics and Its History. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 38-42
79. Usmonov M. T. Asymmetric Cryptosystems. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 6-9.
80. Usmonov M. T. Basic Concepts of Information Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 5-8.
81. Usmonov M. T. Communication Control Systems, Methodology. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 47-50.
82. Usmonov M. T. Compatibility between the Two Package Elements. Binar Relations and Their Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 52-54.
83. Usmonov M. T. Cryptographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-26.
84. Usmonov M. T. Electronic Digital Signature. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 30-34.
85. Usmonov M. T. "Equal" And "Small" Relations. Add. Laws Of Addition. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-29.
86. Usmonov M. T. Establish Network Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-21.
87. Usmonov M. T. Fundamentals of Symmetric Cryptosystem. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
88. Usmonov M. T. General Concepts of Mathematics. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-16.

89. Usmonov M. T. Identification and Authentication. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 39-47.
90. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection and Its Types. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-4.
91. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection in Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 61-64.
92. Usmonov M. T. Information protection supply. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 12-15.
93. Usmonov M. T. Information Security Policy. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 70-73.
94. Usmonov M. T. Information War. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 79-82.
95. Usmonov M. T. International and National Legal Base in the Field Of Information Security. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 7-14.
96. Usmonov M. T. Legal Legislative Basis for Detection of Information Crime. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 80-87.
97. Usmonov M. T. Mathematical Proofs. Incomplete Induction, Deduction, Analogy. The Concept Of Algorithm And Its Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 26-29.
98. Usmonov M. T. Means of Information Protection. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-30.
99. Usmonov M. T. Organization of E-Mail Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
100. Usmonov M. T. Organizing Internet Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-28.

101. Usmonov M. T. Origin and Equal Strength Relationships between Sentences. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions. Structure of Theorem and Their Types. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 45-47.
102. Usmonov M. T. PhysicalSecurity. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
103. Usmonov M. T. Practical Security Management. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 71-74.
104. Usmonov M. T. Problem Solving In Primary Schools. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 72-83.
105. Usmonov M. T. Reproduction. The Laws of Reproduction. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
106. Usmonov M. T. Security Models. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-23.
107. Usmonov M. T. Solving Problems In Arithmetic Methods. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
108. Usmonov M. T. Stenographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 31-35.
109. Usmonov M. T. Telecommunications and Network Security. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 57-61.
110. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.
111. Usmonov M. T. The Concept Of National Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 73-75.
112. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic

Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-21.

113. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Relationship. Characteristics of Relationships. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 38-40.

114. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Size and Measurement. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.

115. Usmonov M. T. The Emergence and Development of Methods of Writing All Negative Numbers. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 48-50.

116. Usmonov M. T. The Purpose, Function and History Of The Development Of Mathematical Science. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 8-17.

117. Usmonov M. T. True and False Thoughts, Quantities. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-5.

118. Usmonov M. T. Virtual Protected Networks. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 55-57.

119. Usmonov M. T. What Is Solving The Problem? Methods of Solving Text Problems. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 56-58.

120. М Усмонув - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105.

121. UM Tulqin o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. DETERMINANTLAR NAZARIYASI. Pages: 232-248.

122. R Jo'rayev, M Usmonov - Solution of social problems in management and ..., 2022. OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING DOLZARBLIGI VA SAMARADORLIGI. Pages: 19-25

123. М Усмонув - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105

124. М Усмонув - Development and innovations in science, 2022. ВЕКТОРНОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. СМЕШАННОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. Pages: 33-52.

125. М Усмонов - Models and methods in modern science, 2022. ДИСКРЕТНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ПОЛИГОН ЧАСТОТ И ЭМПИРИЧЕСКАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ. Pages: 27-35.
126. М Усмонов - Инновационные исследования в науке, 2022. ИНТЕРВАЛЬНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ГИСТОГРАММА ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЧАСТОТ. Pages: 43-52
127. М Усмонов - Международная конференция академических наук, 2022. ФОРМУЛЫ ДЕЛЕНИЯ ОТРЕЗКА В ДАННОМ ОТНОШЕНИИ. ФОРМУЛЫ КООРДИНАТ СЕРЕДИНЫ ОТРЕЗКА. Pages: 17-26.
128. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. YER OSTI SUVLARINING FIZIK XOSSALARI, KIMYOVIY TARKIBI, HARAKATI VA GRUNTLARNING SUV O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI, FILTRATSIYA QONUNI. Pages: 219-222.
129. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. VEKTOR VA SKALYAR MAYDONLAR. GRADIYENT VA YO'NALISH BO'YICHA HOSILA. DIVERGENSIYA VA ROTOR. SATH CHIZIQLARI. GRADIYENT MAYDONLAR. OQIMLAR. Pages: 172-187.
130. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. Pages: 21-33.
131. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21-33. Retrieved from <http://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>
132. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR. DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR FORMULASI VA QATORI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 8-20. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>
133. МТЎ Усмонов, ХУМ Ўғли - Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary ..., 2022. РАВНОМЕРНОЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВЕРОЯТНОСТЕЙ. 15-24
134. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni yechish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
135. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
136. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
137. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

138. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
139. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
140. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Maxsud Tulqin o 'g'li Usmonov maqsudu32@ gmail. com Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Qarshi filiali. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
141. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
142. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
143. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
144. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Kvadratlik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
145. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
146. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko 'paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
147. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
148. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko 'paytmalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.